

ML⁴NGP

MACHINE LEARNING FOR NON GLOBULAR PROTEINS

Science
Communication,
Dissemination and
Exploitation Plan

Document Information

Authors: Rita Vilaça (Science Communication Coordinator); Alexander Monzon (Action Chair); Zuzana Bednarikova (Action Co-chair) | (Document Version 1.0 | 10 May 2023)

Revision: Core Group (Document Version 1.1 | 20 May 2023)

Acceptance: Management Committee (Document version final | Date)

Dissemination Level: Public

Keywords: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation

Abbreviations and acronyms

CG – Core Group

COST – European Cooperation in Science and Technology

EU – European Union

GHM – Grant Holder Manager

IPC – International Partner Countries

ITC – Inclusiveness Target Countries

ITC-CG – Conference Grants for Inclusiveness Target Countries participants

KPI – Key Performance Indicator

ML – Machine Learning

NGP – Non-Globular Proteins

ML4NGP – Machine Learning for Non-Globular Proteins

MC – Management Committee

WG – Working Groups

SCC – Science Communication Coordinator

NNC – Near Neighbour Countries

STSM – Short Term Scientific Missions

Index

1. Introduction	4
2. ML4NGP Action.....	4
2.1. Description	4
2.2. Implementation	4
3. Communication and Dissemination Plan.....	5
3.1. Communication strategy.....	6
3.2 Visual identity and project documentation	7
3.3 Communication tools	7
3.4 Compliance with communication requirements.....	11
4. Dissemination strategy	12
4.1. Dissemination tools	13
4.2. Target stakeholders	15
5. Measuring impact	16
6. Risks and Mitigation Measures	17
7. Exploitation of COST Action and results.....	18
Annex I	20
ML4NGP Brandbook.....	20

1. Introduction

This document defines the communication plan for the Cost Action CA21160 “Non-globular proteins in the Era of Machine Learning”, including how the different tools, channels and means of communication will be implemented throughout the Action duration. The plan also includes information on how the dissemination strategy will target specific groups, outlining key events and actions. It also contains guidelines for implementing all dissemination and communication activities successfully and efficiently by all participants. These guidelines help to ensure that relevant information is shared with appropriate audiences in a timely basis and effective manner. Throughout the project, the dissemination activities will be closely monitored and evaluated. The communication activities will raise awareness about the project activities and disseminate information about its results consistently and coherently to maximize its impact on society.

2. ML4NGP Action

2.1. Description

ML4NGP aims to establish a pan-European network to advance on non-globular protein (NGP) structure and function prediction by reassessing the interplay between experimental and computational data acquired through recent developments of machine learning (ML) approaches and methods for determining NGP structural ensembles. ML4NGP will enhance the primary experimental data generation, promote integrative structural biology approaches, benchmark the state-of-the-art ML methods and improve the functional characterization of NGPs. The generation of new computational techniques, best practices for NGP experimental and computational detection, and the creation of cutting-edge curated datasets will fundamentally contribute to a better understanding and characterization of the relationship between sequence-structure-dynamics-function of NGPs. ML4NGP integrative approaches also aim to raise awareness about NGPs in the scientific community, which has been biased toward globular proteins for many years. The collaborative network between European and non-European projects, societies and initiatives in the field will contribute to raising the awareness of non-globular proteins within and beyond the Action’s participants and the scientific community.

2.2. Implementation

The project is carried out by a high-quality network of different participants from 37 COST member countries in Europe, including 20 Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs), plus one international

partner country (Japan). It is led by the COST Action Chair Dr. Alexander Monzon of the University of Padova in Italy.

This interdisciplinary consortium from 37 countries will work together on 1) NGPs primary experimental data generation, curation and deposition, 2) Machine learning and NGP structural biology, 3) Assessment of state-of-the-art ML approaches in the NGP field, 4) Improving functional characterization of NGPs and 5) Communication, dissemination and exploitation of the Action results and activities. The expected duration of the Action is 48 months.

3. Communication and Dissemination Plan

This document describes a general communication and dissemination plan and specific activities dedicated to the communication of the COST Action ML4NGP and the dissemination of main events and achievements. The main objectives of the communication and dissemination plan are to: Identify the target audiences, communication tools and distribution channels for the successful dissemination and communication of project activities.

Create a project identity through graphically coherent material following visual identity guidelines. Adopt the best strategies for efficiently sharing knowledge by identifying the message and the channel to share each activity and relevant results to which target group.

Define the period for dissemination and communication activities and the responsible partner for the implementation.

Promote dissemination of project outputs to a wide audience through online platforms, promotional materials and events organization/participation.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan is in line with the “Annotated Rules for COST Actions” securing open access and transparency to reach target audiences and the general public. A dedicated Working Group (WG5) will be responsible for the generation and implementation of the plan since the beginning of the project, under the supervision of the Science Communication Coordinator (SCC). The plan will be periodically discussed and evaluated by the Action Management Committee (MC) and the Core Group (CG), and amended if required.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan will be implemented in the scope of the public policy perspective of EU research and innovation funding, aiming to generate value for money from the investment of public funding. This strategy, in line with EU research policy, will allow stakeholders to benefit from the outputs of the project while also being involved and well informed of them.

3.1. Communication strategy

The Communication Plan aims to address activities and communications that will promote the project's progress and outcomes to multiple audiences from the beginning of the project and during the Action's lifetime. The key points of the Action's communication strategy are to:

- Implement effective internal communication among the Action's leadership groups: MC, CG, WGs and the participants;
- Inform and engage the relevant stakeholders in Europe;
- Raise awareness about the project including its main activities, objectives and impact.

By following a defined communication strategy, ML4NGP Action aims to achieve the following communication objectives:

- Prepare a communication toolkit with all features required to ensure a consistent visual identity of the Action;
- Manage the networking tools for the internal communication of the Action;
- Promote actions to communicate the activities and integrative results of the four scientific WGs;
- Assist the organization of symposia, workshops, meetings as well as the Final Conference at the end of the action;
- Implement a continuous communication strategy for the ML4NGP website and social media presence;
- Define strategies for proper communication and dissemination of the main outputs generated by the project to relevant stakeholders and the public;
- Facilitate the communication system for intra- and inter-networking with other relevant organizations with an interest in ML4NGP topics promoting a trustful environment for sharing data and knowledge

Effective communication is critical to the successful implementation of the Action and to ensure that the results are disseminated to the widest possible audience. As part of the communication strategy, different approaches and tools will be used to regularly inform the stakeholders and ensure the visibility of the project. The design and implementation of communication activities should:

- a) Define clear communication objectives, with flexibility for adaptations in the time frame and schedule due to local contexts to achieve maximum impact;
- b) Adapt communication contents and strategies most effectively to specific audiences for each action, considering how and when it should be released and what the nature and content of the dissemination action;
- c) Adopt the best internal communication channels to ensure timely notices for requirements and meetings
- d) Create an Action communication toolkit with the dissemination and communication-supporting material to implement a wider and more effective communication branding
- e) Create awareness and promote Action's outcomes to different stakeholders.

3.2 Visual identity and project documentation

Visual identity is fundamental to creating a clear, coherent, and recognizable brand for all communications and dissemination activities. The Action logo was created by a professional graphic designer based on three key messages of the Action: network, machine learning and disordered protein. The Action and COST logos are incorporated in all public documents, publications and relevant dissemination material to increase Action visibility in compliance with COST communication and visual guidelines. Participants have access to communication tools and templates that should be correctly used and adopted during the Action implementation. The ML4NGP toolkit is deposited in Google Drive and includes:

- Brand Logos and assets
- Brand Typefaces
- Brandbook with visual guidelines (Annex I)
- Template for PowerPoint presentations
- Template for Word documents
- Template for meeting minutes and agenda

3.3 Communication tools

A set of communication tools are used to achieve the most effective communication and reach the defined objectives set by ML4NGP (Table 1).

For **internal communication**, direct communication tools and cloud-based resources includes:

- Slack workspace for instant messaging and channel-based communications
- Google Drive for cloud-based storage of all project assets available for CG members and, whenever required openly shared with all participants of the action
- Mailing lists, for sharing important information among CG and WG members, all members and distributing the Newsletters.
- Zoom (Grant Holder Institutional account) for online communication among the participants of the Action and for WG and CG meetings.

The **external communication** and dissemination activities will be carried out through online platforms and in-person events to diversify and maximize outreach to the target groups and networking with relevant stakeholders, including:

- ML4NGP website, the primary open-access platform for sharing all the activities, actions and results of the Action
- Electronic newsletters, flyers and video-based tools with relevant content
- ML4NGP accounts on social media networks such as Twitter and LinkedIn
- Dissemination events, such as conferences and workshops/training schools, Short Term Scientific Missions (STSMs) and publications

Table 1: Communication channels, tools and goals for ML4NGP Action.

AUDIENCE	CHANNEL		GOAL	TIMELINE
MC and Members	Internal communication	Slack, Zoom	Direct communication about project actions and missions	M3-present
		Mailing lists		M3-present
All stakeholders and public	Online communication	Action website www.ml4ngp.eu	Dissemination of past and upcoming activities, participants and publications	M3-present
		Partner's website	Links to the Action website, and relevant news about the Action	M3-present
		Newsletters	News about the Action with links to the Action website	Starting on M8
Network of Action Members	Social media	Twitter	Action accounts with appropriate hashtags and handles to disseminate project news	M3-present (regular posting)
		Linkedin		
Scientific and specialized communities	Events, workshops and conferences		Presentation of project outputs and results; collaboration and networking	M3-present
	Publications	Scientific publications	Dissemination of Action outputs	M1-present
		Educational training material	Dissemination of Action research and outputs	M6-present
General public and all stakeholders	Information material	Flyers and video-based tools	Dissemination at conferences and scientific events relevant for the Action	M5-present
		Press releases	Dissemination of breakthrough ideas and results of ML4NGP	M1-present
	Local events	Public lectures or national science fairs/events	Dissemination of Action relevance to the society	M3-present

Online communication

The online communication tools will target audiences and stakeholders with interest in Action topics through the Internet. The Action website is the central communication platform for all stakeholders. Communication of Action will also benefit from partners' websites with links to the Action website. In addition, impactful articles will be disseminated through the online press, whenever it benefits Action.

The Grant holder institution will host and keep updated the website, in collaboration with SCC, with news and up-to-date information about scientific events and major Action achievements.

The electronic newsletters will be distributed through mailing lists to Action participants and whenever possible to networks of contacts. Press releases will be prepared whenever required by SCC in close collaboration with Grant Holder Manager (GHM), Chair/Vice Chair and CG members.

ML4NGP website

The Action website (www.ml4ngp.eu) was developed with an open-source platform - Wordpress.com - and serves as the main interface for sharing results and events with all stakeholders and increasing the visibility of the ML4NGP project. Additionally, it gives information about Action's participants - CG and MC members - and relevant partners, including their contact details and their role within ML4NGP widening the team to future collaborative networking. It also includes links to social networking and professional websites.

The public area of the website provides general information on the scientific topics and background research, project objectives, working groups description, and an event calendar with meetings, conferences and training schools. The website is the central repository for educational material that will be collected from Action training events and available resources/tools and experimental data developed within the framework or related to the project. The website has a contact form for anyone interested in the project or who wishes to join Action by mailing the form directly to the Action Chair and the GHM. A News blog-like section is displayed on the top menu of the home page and is constantly updated with relevant information.

The website includes the Action logo, the COST features, the COST logo and the EU emblem and funding acknowledgements.

The website will be online for a minimum of 10 years including the duration of the project.

Social media

Social media strategy success relies on regular posting with appropriate content considering the target audience. The underlying concept of these technologies is networking which will also depend on the participation of all WG participants and their ability to constantly interact with followers that

have an interest in the Action. To promote the visibility of Action, a Twitter account was created [@ml4ngp](https://twitter.com/ml4ngp).

The most relevant information uploaded on the Action website will be shared across the Action social media accounts. The Action members will share Action's relevant information through their own institutional social media accounts (LinkedIn and Twitter). The SCC will ensure that relevant information will also be distributed through the official social media account of the COST Association (<https://twitter.com/COSTprogramme>, <https://www.linkedin.com/company/costoffice>). This strategy will result in more visibility for the project and improve networking and dissemination at European level.

When communicating on Twitter or other social media about ML4NGP project activities and results, always use the following:

- hashtags: #ml4ngp, #COSTactions, #ScienceWithoutBorders
- handles: @ml4ngp, @COSTprogramme, @EU_Commission

Wikipedia articles

ML4NGP will contribute to Wikipedia through thematic articles sharing state of the art methods and applications in the NGP and ML field, experimental and computational protocols for protein structure determination and relevant Action publications.

Flyers and informative video-based tools

A general flyer with information about the Action, the main objectives, the topics of each working group and participants will be prepared in the first months of the project to be distributed to relevant target audiences in electronic format. Short and simple texts will be integrated with images to illustrate the message. The flyer will also contain information for anyone with an interest in the project to join the Action.

If relevant and whenever justifiable, other flyers will be produced for dissemination of Action achievements with infographics containing data interesting for specific stakeholders.

Short informative videos (1-3 minutes) will be developed during the Action to explore basic concepts and key messages for undefined and non-specialist audiences. These videos, once produced by an external graphic designer, can be used for outreach activities and made available on the Action website for educational purposes even after Action's lifetime.

Newsletters

Newsletters will be published and distributed every 6 months to the action participants (as defined in Memorandum of Understanding), reporting Action activities and results to promote awareness about Action impact and network. The content for each Newsletter will be edited by the Action chair, vice-chair and SCC in collaboration with CG. The main contents of the Newsletters will include:

- Welcome note by Action chairs
- A schematic overview of Action achievements on each period
- Reporting of events during the period
- Upcoming events and important information, including dates
- Progress of the Action with measuring impact
- Short interviews with Action participants, CG and MC members

Press releases and media

Press releases will be developed during the Action timeline as a way to increase external awareness of Action's major achievements. A general press release will be prepared in the first months for dissemination of the starting period of ML4NGP Action by the Grant Holder Institution. Press releases will be shared with local and national media and will be posted on Action website for further accessibility of any interested parties.

Whenever appropriate and relevant, members of the Action will engage with the local and national media.

3.4 Compliance with communication requirements

The presence of COST brand identity and EU funding acknowledgement (Figure 1) will be present in all communication tools developed for the Action following the rules defined in [COST Action Visual Branding Guidelines](#) and in compliance with the Annotated Rules for COST Actions – Point 5.1.

The following statement will be included in all Open Access scientific publications, including articles in scientific journals and books:

This article/publication is based upon work from COST Action ML4NGP, CA21160, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology).

Figure 1: COST logo and EU acknowledgement logo.

A document with ML4NGP brand guidelines (in Appendix I) is found on the ML4NGP Communication Toolkit and should be consulted by all participants for preparation of any material for Action dissemination.

4. Dissemination strategy

The dissemination plan will follow the COST Principle of Openness based on Open Science with strategies to ensure high-quality innovative research results and collaborative dissemination of the ML4NGP and its outcomes. The dissemination strategy targets groups with expertise in the field and potential end-users, including scientific community, public authorities, suppliers and industry.

The main dissemination objectives for ML4NGP are:

- Organization of actions to disseminate the activities and results to relevant stakeholders
- Preparation and dissemination of action materials to raise awareness and create interest in the action topics, including publications, following principles of Open Science and Open Access
- Promotion of the action via the use of informational (poster and presentations) and promotional materials (newsletters, flyers, brochures, etc.) in workshops or conferences in which ML4NGP members will participate

The Action will specifically target NNCs and ITCs by promoting synergies with relevant projects sharing the same aims and/or fields of study and by fostering the participation of members in Action's events.

To reach the defined objectives, a set of dissemination activities will be implemented, including open-access scientific publications and guidelines, the organization of workshops and conferences and demonstrations in scientific events. These dissemination activities also envision promoting more research collaborations widening the COST Action beyond the initial participants.

Furthermore, it creates the foundation for the effective exploitation of the ML4NGP outcomes. They will be built around scientific dissemination tools and communication strategies in order to expand knowledge and engage a wider audience.

4.1. Dissemination tools

A set of tools and activities will establish an effective dissemination and public disclosure of project results to end users. The Action website is a hybrid digital platform both for communication and dissemination purposes.

Conferences, training schools and workshops

The Action will organize several scientific events to promote the dissemination of project results and achievements, and favor networking among participants. To increase visibility and integration of researchers from countries within the Action network, we will organize yearly **conferences** in ITCs. These conferences will provide a platform for researchers to share their knowledge and findings. In addition, we will conduct training schools that target early-stage researchers to provide them with the latest advances and technologies in the NGP field. The **training schools** will equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge to contribute to the development of the field. The **workshops** will provide an opportunity to engage with experts in the field to discuss upcoming challenges and re-evaluate our working group activities. Through these discussions, we aim to identify innovative solutions and strategies to overcome challenges and enhance the impact of our work. The insights and feedback obtained from these workshops will help us to refine our approach and ensure that our working group activities align with current trends and best practices in the field. Moreover, members of the Action will be encouraged to participate in **conferences organized by third parties** to present scientific results maximizing the exposure and impact of Action results towards the scientific community and industrial partners. A list of relevant upcoming scientific events will be constantly updated on the Action website, together with guidelines for the mobility grant awarding process for researchers and innovators to promote their engagement for showcasing Action achievements.

Publications

Following a policy of transparency and Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) data sharing, the Action will encourage the submission of original open access papers and reviews jointly published in peer-reviewed journals. Moreover, educational material collected from Action training events (including Training Schools) will be available for all stakeholders and interested third parties on the Action website and deposited on Zenodo Community.

One or more brochures will be created for the partners to distribute nationally, or at conferences. Open-source code will be developed using the rules available in www.opensource.org/licenses. Lay information, including citizen science projects (e.g. <http://scistarter.com/>) will be distributed with clear messages to reach society.

Educational material

The website will host open access major outputs of ML4NGP and relevant material such as educational material collected from Action Training events (such as Training Schools), freeware tools developed by the Action partners and relevant publications from within and beyond the Action.

Participants

The SCC in close cooperation with the Action Chairs and WG leaders will be responsible for the project's dissemination and communication plan, guarantee consistency in the message delivered and ensure all the targets are successfully reached. All partners will contribute to the implementation of networking strategies to target stakeholders and promote public engagement with the Action. Specifically, Action members will be responsible for:

- Creating a bridge between the project and the networks they are involved in;
- Providing input to the content of the project's website, communication materials and media channels;
- Disseminating the activities and results of the project through their institutional social media channels;
- Disseminating the activities and results of the project at local and national events/fairs.

The SCC and WG5 members will coordinate and manage the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan of ML4NGP. The key responsibilities of the SCC include:

- Plan and coordinate the implementation of communication activities at the project level;
- Create content and a timeline for relevant news for the website and regular postings for Action's social media accounts;
- Support all internal and external communications;
- Maintain records of all communication activities and project outputs for periodical and final reporting;
- Be the central point of contact with the Cost Association for communication activities and regularly inform the COST Science officer about Action's communication activities (events, conferences and workshops, publications, press releases, etc.);
- Coordinate the Final Action Dissemination (FAD) grant in close collaboration with CG members.

The dissemination activities will directly involve researchers from NNC, ITC and IPC countries by supporting intra-network communities in the organization of topic-specific meetings, training schools and STSMs.

The engagement of relevant stakeholders with the project (eg. Biotech stakeholders, national and international scientific societies, European infrastructures initiatives, EU-funded consortia, scientific

platforms for dissemination of relevant news and achievements, etc.) will ensure effective dissemination reaching a broader audience.

The representative members of each country will be responsible for disseminating the activities of the Action to research groups within their countries, industrial partners, societies, and representatives of the society.

4.2. Target stakeholders

The activities of the Action will be disseminated as widely as possible to the following stakeholders (Table 2):

- Scientific community and Universities
- Academics
- Pharma and Biotech companies
- EU member states, regulatory bodies and policymakers (including the European Commission)
- International scientific community, including scientific societies
- General public

An effective dissemination strategy will promote the engaging of the stakeholders with the Action by:

- Sharing research results
- Stimulating new research projects
- Raising awareness of the Action topic with the general public and among scientific societies
- Influencing policy making
- Creating an open access platform for facilitating the alignment of scientific research with academia and societal needs

Table 2: Stakeholders and the potential impact of the Action outputs.

STAKEHOLDER	DISSEMINATION ACTION	PROJECT IMPACT
All	Website	Raise awareness of Action achievements and quality of European research in the NGPs field
Scientific community	Conferences, Workshops and Training Schools; Participation in scientific meetings organized by third parties; Open Access Scientific Publications; Social media	Transfer of knowledge to young researchers and interest scientific communities
Academics		Introduction of ML4NGP topics into pre-graduate curricula for

		capacitation of future generation of researchers
Pharma and Biotech companies	Informative Brochures; press releases; video based-tools; wikipedia articles; social media	Development of new technologies and processes possibly adaptable by the R&D industries
Local, national and European Regulatory bodies and policymakers	Participation in local and national public science events; educational visits to high-schools; press-releases and media presence.	Introduction of ML4NGP topics into pre-graduate curricula for capacitation of future generation of researchers
General public		Raise awareness of the impact of NL4NGP research in society and the impact of public funded research.

5. Measuring impact

The effectiveness and efficiency of the actions for information and public awareness depend on both the communication channel and the message's content. The target audience should be able to recognize the information and further understand the message. In order to measure the efficacy of the tools described in this Plan, the SCC will keep track of key performance indicators (KPI) that will determine the efficient implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan during the Action:

- Number of visits to the Action website.
- Appearances in media (e.g. articles published in press/online, interviews, etc.).
- Number of events attended by network members relevant to the Action.
- Number of presentations of the Action at conferences or events (presentation, poster, paper).
- Number of conferences, STSMs, Conference Grants, training schools, workshops, and other events.
- Number of participants in Action events.
- Number of newsletters and flyers.
- Number of recipients/subscribers of the Action's newsletter.
- Tweet impressions and engagements on the Action's Twitter account and re-tweets.
- Number of members and followers of social media accounts
- Number of scientific publications and protocols.
- Number of press releases and media presence

Whenever necessary, SCC and WG5 members will adapt the communication and dissemination strategies to improve KPI after MC approval. In addition, Action partners must ensure that:

- Signed list of participants is kept for all workshops, conferences, seminars and events organized under the project in a hardcopy
- Presentations are in accordance with the specific templates provided
- Photos are being taken as evidence of action implementation after signed consent form
- Action and COST and EU funding are well acknowledged in all dissemination material

6. Risks and Mitigation Measures

The implementation of the communication plan can be influenced by a wide range of factors, both internal and external. The major risk for project failure is due to ineffective or lack of communication. In the beginning of the Action, ML4NGP CG identified possible risks on the Action plan for project communication and dissemination and procedures to help mitigate the appointed risks to reach the success of the Action implementation (Table 3).

Table 3: Risks and mitigation measures for the implementation of the Action science communication and dissemination plan.

RISKS	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
Low level of engagement/Disengagement of Action members	Ensure sustainable communication and equal interaction with regular updates on activities and results; reinforce the use of internal communication tools
Low level of awareness about ML4NGP activities from the stakeholders	Adopt a content management strategy with regular updates on the Action website and interesting posts/tweets on Action's social media channels to engage the attention of followers and end-users; organization of meetings and workshops to engage and interact directly with stakeholders
Lack of consistency and dedication of Action members in the communication activities	Set-up regular meetings with SCC and WG5 to define the content and schedule of communication activities

Non-compliance with Action visual identity guidelines and agreed templates	Templates will be made available from the beginning of the project. SCC will monitor the usage of templates and the visual identity guidelines and intervene whenever necessary.
Weak communication of project results and achievements by the Action partners at the local, national and European level	The SCC will periodically monitor KPIs and will discuss progress and strategies to counteract it with CG and Chair/Vice-Chair

7. Exploitation of COST Action and results

The objective of exploitation activities is to maximize the impact of the research outcomes and knowledge transfer. The following measures will be taken:

Table 4: Implementation of strategic guidelines for exploitation of Action results and outputs.

EXPLOITABLE RESULTS		STRATEGIC IMPLEMENTATION
Research outcomes and outputs Research outcomes and outputs	Research outcomes and outputs can be produced inside the network, including scientific publications, experimental protocols, technical reports, software tools, and datasets.	Developing new standards or guidelines: ML4NGP may lead to the development of new standards or guidelines based on the NGP field. These standards or guidelines can be used to promote best practices in the field and to ensure the quality of research or products.
Partners and collaborators	The COST action will identify and collaborate with several partners and collaborators, including other COST actions, industry partners, and funding agencies. These collaborations led to further research advancements and facilitated the transfer of technology and knowledge to industry.	Developing new collaborations: ML4NGP may lead to the development of new collaborations between researchers or between researchers and industry. These collaborations can help to further develop the research outcomes, and to promote their exploitation.

Funding and resources	The COST action secured funding from the European Union and other sources, which will be used to support research activities, travel, and dissemination activities.	Providing evidence for grant applications: The outcomes of this COST Action can provide evidence for grant applications, which can be used to secure additional funding for further research in the field, empowered by the new collaborations developed during the Action.
Implementation and monitoring	The exploitation plan will be implemented and monitored throughout the lifecycle of the COST action. Regular feedback from stakeholders, evaluation of impact and sustainability goals, and adjustment of the plan as needed will ensure its success.	

By implementing these exploitation strategies, COST Actions can ensure that their outcomes have a lasting impact beyond the Action lifetime. Moreover, the involvement of stakeholders from the beginning of the Action will ensure aligned research and knowledge creation with both scientific communities and societal needs. This strategy will potentiate the exploitation and valorization of Action major outcomes ensuring that all stakeholders identified will benefit directly from the Action achievements and the perdurance of the generated knowledge and value.

Annex I

ML4NGP Brandbook

ml4ngp brand guidelines

identity manual

This guide explains what our brand stands for, how it's expressed, and how the creative elements fit together in all our communications.

It should inspire and encourage more effective communications whenever they carry ml4ngp logo.

trademarks

- 5 logo
- 6 logo lockup
- 7 symbol
- 8 clear space
- 9 scale
- 10 versions
- 11 incorrect usage
- 12 placement

color

- 14 color palette
- 15 gradient

typography

- 17 say hello to our fonts

brand is use

- 19 samples

trademarks

logo

Our logo consists of two elements: symbol (it represents neural network, community, protein and disorder protein) and wordmark.

It's an instantly recognisable brand element and should be represented consistently throughout our documents and marketing efforts.

The horizontal logo is our main logo and should be used in most instances. However, in exceptional cases where there is not enough space for it, you can use the stacked version instead.

Always use the logo files provided. Do not re-create.

[download assets](#)

HORIZONTAL LOGO

VERTICAL OR STACKED LOGO

logo lockup

Our logo lockup is only used in the disrupt part of our own communication or when we exist in a context where the nature of our business isn't obvious. This ensures we tell the customer what we are all about in a rational way.

"Machine learning for non globular proteins" is the only tagline to be used in a lockup. Never create your own taglines or lockups.

Avoid using our logo lockup at small sizes, as it can become illegible.

HORIZONTAL LOGO

VERTICAL OR STACKED LOGO

symbol

Our symbol results from the combination of three different elements: neural network, structured protein and disorder protein.

Our symbol should be used as the reduced form of our logo in tight spaces.

Neural network

Structured protein

Disorder protein

Machine Learning For
Non Globular Proteins

clear space

To ensure the right amount of breathing space around our logo the following process should be applied:

LOGO

The minimum clear space of the logo is the width of the letter "M".

ICON

The minimum clear space of the icon is a third of its height.

scale

In order to maintain legibility, our logo and icon should never appear smaller than these minimum sizes.

Digital applications

In digital applications, whenever possible, use our logo in a scalable vector graphics (SVG) format to maximize legibility and scalability.

In other formats, please adjust the logo according to the screen resolution (i.e., @2x for Retina Display and @3x for iPhone 6 Plus).

PRINT

DIGITAL

versions

There are three approved versions :

Color

This is the standard version of the logo for use in digital and full- color print applications.

Black

For use in limited-color printed applications and on light-colored backgrounds.

White

For use in limited-color printed applications, dark-color backgrounds, gradients and photo backgrounds.

These rules apply to symbol and logo lockup as well.

COLOR

BLACK

WHITE

WHITE

incorrect usage

In order to preserve the integrity of the logo, the following examples illustrate how it should not be used.

These rules apply to the icon as well.

DON'T stretch or compress

DON'T add drop shadows

DON'T recolor

DON'T use without the symbol

DON'T outline

DON'T change the size of elements relative to each other

placement

Always place the logo or icon within the margins. Preferred place is aligned to the top left corner, top right corner, bottom left corner, bottom right corner, or centred of the application.

Do not place the logo on vertical format.

These rules apply to symbol and logo lockup as well.

color

color palette

Our color palette is made up three hero colors: Blue Pantone, St. Patricks Blue and Maximum Red.

Color specifications are provided for the following color profiles: RGB, HEX and Process (CMYK).

[download assets](#)

BLUE PANTONE

HEX 111E9D
RGB 17, 30, 157
CMYK 89, 81, 0, 38

ST PATRICKS BLUE

HEX 3B2E72
RGB 59, 46, 114
CMYK 70, 75, 0, 70

MAXIMUM RED

HEX E40713
RGB 228, 7, 19
CMYK 0, 97, 92, 11

gradient

Our gradient is built from two colors: Blue Pantone and Maximum Red. The gradient can be build in vectors (Adobe Illustrator) or pixels (Adobe Photoshop) using the gradient tool.

Always ensure that the Blue Pantone starts the left side and finishes with the Maximum Red.

location: 14%

0° angle

location: 82%

BLUE PANTONE

HEX 111E9D
RGB 17, 30, 157
CMYK 89, 81, 0, 38

MAXIMUM RED

HEX E40713
RGB 228, 7, 19
CMYK 0, 97, 92, 11

typography

say hello to our fonts

Sofia Pro

Sofia Pro is a Google font. It offers great balance as it is slightly more clean. This is our font of choice.

Poppins

Poppins is also a Google font. In order to maintain maximum visual consistency throughout the brand, when Sofia Pro is not available you may use Poppins.

Aero 03

Aero 03 helps us to express our personality and makes our brand unique. This is the font of our logo.

[download assets](#)

SOFIA PRO FAMILY

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm
Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Xx Yy Zz
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

POPPINS

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm
Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Xx Yy Zz
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

AERO 03

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm
Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Xx Yy Zz
0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

brand in use

 ML⁴NGP

ML⁴NGP

About us

Non-globular proteins in the era of Machine Learning (ML4NGP)

Protein structure prediction has long been considered the "Holy Grail" of structural biology. The recent success of AlphaFold has ushered in a new era of highly accurate structure prediction, bringing to light the secrets hidden in the three-dimensional structures of globular proteins, increasing our understanding about their structural features and molecular function.

However, a large proportion of the proteomes from all domains of life are rich in sequences that do not fold into regular structures, commonly known as non-globular proteins (NGPs). NGPs comprise intrinsically disordered regions, repeats, low-complexity sequences, aggregation-prone and phase-separating sequences, and are implicated in a range of age-related diseases.

thanks

